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Abstract Book

BUILDING CONNECTIONS FOR GLOBAL GEOCONSERVATION

Editors: G. Lozano, J. Luengo, A. Cabrera
and J. Vegas

10th International ProGEO online Symposium

ABSTRACT BOOK

**BUILDING CONNECTIONS FOR
GLOBAL GEOCONSERVATION**

Editors

Gonzalo Lozano, Javier Luengo, Ana Cabrera and Juana Vegas

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Geological heritage in the Valleys of Cantabria Geopark project

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Keywords: geomorphological features, geosites inventory, geotourism, UNESCO Global Geopark, Valleys of Cantabria aspiring Geopark.

Geographical and geological setting of the aspiring Geopark

The Commonwealth of Sustainable Municipalities (*Mancomunidad de Municipios Sostenibles de Cantabria, MMS*), under the assistance of the University of Cantabria (UC), is promoting the candidacy, for the UNESCO Geosciences and Geoparks Programme, of *Valles de Cantabria* in northern Spain since 2018. The territory of the proposed Geopark covers an area of 592.8 km², including 19 municipalities and about 60.000 inhabitants. It is situated in the eastern part of Cantabria (Fig. 1A), bordering the provinces of Burgos and Vizcaya; the area is characterised by steep slopes, with heights ranging from 0 to 1600 m above sea level, where *Miera* and *Asón* rivers shape the landscape of these valleys.

From a geological point of view, the aspiring Geopark is located in the eastern sector of the Cantabrian Mountain Range in the Basque-Cantabrian Basin (García-Mondéjar et al., 1996), where rocks from the Mesozoic age (Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous, with ages ranging from 230 to 94 Ma) are overlapped by a wide variety of quaternary deposits (Fig. 1B).

Geological heritage in the aspiring Geopark

In the Valleys of Cantabria aspiring Geopark, the most representative geological context, included in the Global Geosites project (listed in Annex VIII of Law 42/2007 and its modification in Law 33/2015 on natural heritage and biodiversity), are:

- Coasts of the Iberian Peninsula.
- Carbonate and evaporite karst systems.
- Pb-Zn and Fe mineralizations of the Urgonian of the Basque-Cantabrian basin.

Fig. 1. A) The situation of the applicant territory, including municipalities, rivers and main roads. B) Geological map (Triassic, Jurassic, Cretaceous materials, and Quaternary deposits) with the location of Geosites.

Additionally, the most representative geologic units represented in this aspiring Geopark are:

- Unique geological structures and formations of the basement, allochthonous units and Mesozoic cover of the Alpine Mountains.

- Unique structures and geological formations of the Cenozoic continental and marine basins.
- Deposits, edaphic soils and unique modelling forms representative of the action of the current and past climate.

The *Asón* and *Miera* valleys show a high-quality landscape, due to the diversity of their geomorphological features. Landforms in the area are the result of the dismantling of pre-existing relief due to erosive agents that have acted in the area during the Quaternary and the combination of tectonic movements. As result, an excellent representation of different geomorphological landscapes (to be highlighted: coastal and wind, fluvial, karst, slope and glaciers), as well as stratigraphic, tectonic, and paleontological features, can be observed in this area. However, this territory is characterized by the presence of glacial processes and forms, and the underground heritage. An extensive network of underground systems, associated to carbonate rocks of Cretaceous age, is developed generating exokarst and endokarst geofoms. On the other hand, the coastal area concentrates a high variety of each of the natural environments typical of mid-latitude coastal areas, which makes it highly representative (*Marismas of Santoña* is catalogued as Wetlands of International Importance on the Ramsar List, estuarine areas, beaches, dune systems, etc.).

66 Sites of Geological Interest were inventoried in the territory and a worksheet has been completed for each one of these sites according to the methodology proposed by Hilario et al. (2017). These Geosites have been classified according to their geological interest in: geomorphologic, paleoclimatic, structural, hydrogeological, sedimentological, petrological, paleontological, stratigraphic, metallogenic, and cultural; by their relevance, scientific value, main use (scientific, educational, geotourism) or the existence of any protection figure. The total number of Geosites, 45 have had a high or very high evaluation, due to their scientific, educational or geo-tourist value. Moreover, **8 Geosites of international relevance** are presented in the area. Miera Glacier valley is attributed to the Marine Isotope Stage MIS2 and MIS3 episodes (Rodríguez et al., 2015), with the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) established between 44,000 and 29,000 years before the present (B.P.) (Serrano et al., 2013); Iron Mineralization in Peña Cabarga Paleokarst, Matienzo poljé, Hydrogeological System and karren of Mortillano (more than 4,000 cavities are catalogued in the area, León-García, 2010); Liendo Diapir, Sonabia Dunes, Asón Estuary and Covalanas Cave (declared in 2008 a UNESCO World Heritage Site, due to the importance of its cave paintings); **13 of national relevance; 15 of regional relevance and 30 of local relevance** (MMS, 2020). Some of these geosites require geoconservation actions; other, are suitable for the development of scientific or geotourism activities.

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Geodiversity in the aspiring Valleys of Cantabria Geopark

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INTRODUCTION

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GEOLOGICAL HERITAGE IN THE ASPIRING GEOPARK

In the Valleys of Cantabria aspiring Geopark, the most representative geological context, included in the Global Geosites project are:

- Coasts of the Iberian Peninsula.
- Carbonate and evaporite karst systems.
- Pb-Zn and Fe mineralizations of the Urganian of the Basque-Cantabrian basin.

Additionally, the most representative geologic units represented in this aspiring Geopark are:

- Unique geological structures and formations of the basement, allochthonous units and Meso-Cenozoic cover of the Alpine Mountains.
- Unique structures and geological formations of the Cenozoic continental and marine basins.
- Deposits, edaphic soils and unique modelling forms representative of the action of the current and past climate.

8 Geosites of international relevance are presented in the area

66 Sites of Geological Interest were inventoried in the territory

13 of national relevance; 15 of regional relevance and 30 of local relevance

8 Geosites of international relevance are presented in the area, Miera Glacier valley; Iron Mineralization in Peña Cabarga Paleokarst, Matienzo polje, Hydrogeological System and karren of Mortillano (more than 4,000 cavities are catalogued in the area, León-García, 2010); Liendo Diapir, Sonabia Dunes, Asón Estuary and Covallanas Cave (declared in 2008 a UNESCO World Heritage Site, due to the importance of its cave paintings)

These Geosites have been classified according to their geological interest in: *geomorphologic, paleoclimatic, structural, hydrogeological, sedimentological, petrological, stratigraphic, metallogenic, and cultural*; by their relevance, scientific value, main use (scientific, educational, geotourism) or the existence of any protection figure.

The total number of Geosites, 45 have had a high or very high evaluation, due to their scientific, educational or geotourist value.

The *Asón* and *Miera* valleys show a high-quality landscape, due to the diversity of their geomorphological features. This territory is characterized by the presence of glacial processes and forms, and the underground heritage. An extensive network of underground systems, associated to carbonate rocks of Cretaceous age, is developed generating exokarst and endokarst geofoms. On the other hand, the coastal area concentrates a high variety of each of the natural environments typical of mid-latitude coastal areas.

